

UTC-UTI YEAR 2 JOURNAL ARTICLES

Year 2 (5/2018 to 10/2018) Journal Articles from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI)

Journal Papers:

01. Kravitz, B., Mooney, M., Karlovsek, J., Danielson, I., Hedayat, A. (2019) "Void detection in two-component annulus grout behind a pre-cast segmental tunnel liner using Ground Penetrating Radar." Tunn Undergr Sp Tech 83, 381-392. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tust.2018.09.032>
02. Shirole, D., Walton, G., Ostrovsky, L., Masoumi, H., Hedayat, A. (2018) "Non-linear ultrasonic monitoring of damage progression in disparate rocks." Int J Rock Mech Min 111, 33-44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrmms.2018.08.010>